

Experimental Report P8476, MID September 25-30 2024
Coherent Modulation X-ray Imaging and wavefront sensing

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We were given 2 days as in-house beamtime to perform proof of concept experiment for use of coherent modulation imaging (CMI)[1] / coherent speckle correlation (CSI)[2] alike diffuser-based setup for high resolution wavefront sensing and imaging. This novel technique utilizes the known random diffuser with nm-scale features in the near field of the sample of interest to modulate either exit wave after the sample (wavefront sensing / shadow imaging geometry) or illumination function before the sample (imaging geometry). The known modulation enables robust and high-fidelity phase retrieval from the single diffraction pattern. Additionally, produced speckled diffraction patterns have reduced dynamical range in comparison to usual far-field diffraction from the sample allowing to have more photons on the detector before it's saturation. This make this technique ideal for single-shot imaging or wavefront sensing experiments at FELs enabling time-resolved measurements via pump-probe. This experiment is the continuation of the P-5936

Figure 2. Experimental setup for the diffuser-downstream geometry (wavefront sensing/ shadow imaging). The beam focused by CRLs hits the sample and then propagates to randomized diffuser scattering the beam to the detector.

Figure 1. Ptychographic reconstructions of the diffuser and sample transfer functions (B,D) and illumination wavefield at the respective planes (A, C)

E). The knowledge of the experiment geometry and the diffuser TF allows to perform single-shot reconstructions of the wavefield on the diffuser plane. Randomized structure of the diffuser results in strong constraints in phase retrieval algorithm enabling single-shot reconstruction from random initialization without the a priori support knowledge with the robustness and resolution comparable to ptychography as shown in Figure 3. A) and B) are intensity of the illumination at the diffuser plane reconstructed with

We performed the measurements in two experimental geometries. First, we performed the measurements in the diffuser-downstream geometry shown in Figure 1. The X-ray beam had a photon energy of 9keV. We used a pink beam with 30 eV (SASE) bandwidth with 10Hz repetition rate. The 50 Be compound refractive lenses (CRLs) focused the incoming x-rays to 100 nm with a focal length of 300 mm. The Jungfrau detector placed roughly 955 cm downstream the focus at was used for the measurements 10 Hz. Siemens star (Au on Si) resolution target was located 10 mm downstream the focus on a piezo stage (PI). The diffuser (W with through holes on Si used in [1]) was located 10 mm downstream the

sample in a second set of piezo motors (SmarAct). In this geometry the X-ray beam first hits the sample resulting in the presence of the Siemens star 'shadow' in the exit wave. Next, the exit-wave propagates to the diffuser where it becomes strongly modulated and scatters to the detector placed in the far field.

We measured the following datasets: ptychography on the diffuser with diffuser-in sample-out then ptychography on the sample with the diffuser-out, finally we measured several datasets with the sample-in and diffuser-in.

The data were processed using the in-house developed software package for ptychography and cmi at FELs [3].

The results of the ptychography reconstructions are shown in Figure 2. A) B) are the diffuser TF and the illumination function at the diffuser reconstructed with ptychography. C) D) are the sample TF and the illumination function reconstructed with ptychography.

Beam propagation in the experiment geometry is shown in

Figure 3. Illumination intensity at the diffuser plane reconstructed with ptychography (A) (3000 measured diffraction patterns) and CMI (B) (single diffraction pattern).

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ptychography and CMI respectively. They demonstrate compatible reconstruction quality, while being produced from dramatically different number of the measured diffraction patterns (3000 and 1 for ptychography and CMI respectively).

Figure 4. Reconstructed illumination wavefields (D-F) on the diffuser surface with correct diffuser position (A), incorrect diffuser position (B) and 2X larger field of view at the diffuser plane (C). The algorithm reliably converging and even capable to provide reconstructions with double field of view.

Moreover, CMI does not require the known illumination position on the diffuser TF and can be used with extended reconstructed TF as illustrated in Figure 4. The randomly-initialized illumination function converges to the correct one with both correctly (A,) and incorrectly (B,) positioned diffuser TF while showing its correct position, The extended diffuser TF(C) also can be used enlarging the FOV in the diffuser plane.

The dataset measured with the sample-in diffuser-in in was processed to reconstruct the wavefield on the diffuser plane Figure 5 (A-C) which was propagated to the assumed sample plane (D-F) to check if it will be possible to resolve the shadow of the sample. As shown at Figure 5 () it is possible to resolve the smallest features of the Siemens Star (20 nm) staring with the random initialization which proves high-resolution and robustness of the CMI for single-shot wavefront sensing and imaging.

Figure 5. Example of the 'shadow imaging' with diffuser. (A-C) Reconstructed wave field intensity at the diffuser plane for various sample position. (D-F) Reconstructions back-propagated to the sample plane, The shadow of the Siemens star is visible. Smallest feature size is 20 nm.

The second experiment geometry had the diffuser laced upstream the sample as shown in Figure. This modulates the beam in the known way before illuminating the sample of interest enabling the single-shot reconstructions as in randomized probe imaging [4].

As previously we have measured three datasets (sample-in diffuser-out, sample-out diffuser-in, and sample0in diffuser-in). This dataset is still in processing. We have finished the ptychographic reconstructions obtaining the diffuser and sample TFs and the corresponding illumination functions and estimated experiment geometry. The processing of the single-shot dataset is expected to be completed in 2 months.

Figure 8. Experimental setup for the diffuser-upstream geometry (imaging). The beam focused by CRLs is modulated by the diffuser placed in the near field of the sample of interest. The known modulation imprints nano-scale structure into the beam making possible the single-shot phase retrieval.

Step size: 0.05002 mm, D plane index: 1000, Diff plane index: 1510, SS from D: 25.51 mm

A

Figure 6. Figure 7. Ptychographic reconstructions of the diffuser and sample transfer functions (E, D) and illumination wavefield at the respective planes (C, B). The experimental geometry estimated from back-propagation (A).

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References:

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